

1 Functional annotation - how to tackle the bottleneck 2 in plant genomics

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15 Abstract

16 Long read sequencing enables the cost-effective sequencing of plant DNA and assembly of
17 highly continuous genome sequences - often even separating haplophases. Incorporating
18 external hints, such as cDNA sequences from RNA-seq or full length cDNA sequencing,
19 enhances the identification of gene models. While these steps enable high-throughput
20 exploration of numerous plant genomes, a significant bottleneck lies in elucidating gene
21 functions. The classical approach based on wet lab methods is impractical when dealing with
22 thousands of genes in a new genome sequence. To overcome this challenge, computational
23 tools harnessing existing information for cross species knowledge transfer are essential for
24 expediting the functional annotation process. In support of researchers entering the field of plant
25 genomics, a collection of recommended tools has been curated and is accessible at
26 <https://github.com/PuckerLab/FunctionalAnnotation>.

27
28 **Keywords:** functional annotation, orthologs, cross-species transfer, artificial intelligence

29 Introduction

30 Rapid advancements in long read sequencing technologies have enabled access to high quality
31 plant genome sequences in an unprecedented manner (Pucker *et al.* 2022; de Oliveira *et al.*
32 2026). Further with the dawn of the artificial intelligence era, finding genes in these sequences
33 i.e., the process of structural annotation has also reached new heights with deep learning-based
34 structural annotators (Gabriel *et al.* 2024; Holst *et al.* 2025). Despite these developments,
35 methods to obtain knowledge of gene function have still got a long way to go. Functional
36 annotation is defined as obtaining the details of a gene's biological identity and role (Berardini *et*
37 *al.* 2004). Functional annotation of a gene is crucial to establish its genomic context, and
38 understand its role in various biological processes that can have practical implications in

39 metabolic engineering and synthetic biology (Kasif & Steffen 2010). As will be discussed later,
40 wet lab experiments using classical genetics approaches, although highly accurate, are
41 extremely tedious, and time consuming on a large scale. This necessitates effective
42 computational approaches with high throughput for expediting the functional annotation process.
43 This involves classifying genes and gene families based on their history of evolution and
44 divergence. The comparative genomics community uses specific terms to denote genes based
45 on different modes of divergence in their evolutionary trajectory. The terms are as follows -
46 'homologs' - general term used to denote genes that descend from the same ancestor',
47 'orthologs' - homologs that diverged due to a speciation event, 'paralogs' - homologs that
48 diverged due to a gene duplication event, and 'xenologs' - homologs that arose out of a
49 horizontal gene transfer event (Majidian, Hadziahmetovic, *et al.* 2025). However, there are
50 challenges involved in delineating these different homolog classes in comparative genomics.
51 Events like differential gene loss, domain shuffling and the presence of orphan genes, are major
52 road blocks in understanding gene function. This in turn acts as a barrier for cross-species
53 transfer of gene functions (Langschieid *et al.* 2024; Majidian, Hadziahmetovic, *et al.* 2025).
54 Nevertheless, the past decade has seen some progress in this direction through the synergy of
55 a number of comparative genomics approaches like phylogeny and synteny. This has resulted
56 in a number of computational tools relevant for gene function unravelling.

57
58 In this context, the following review is envisioned as a go-to functional annotation guide for
59 researchers, specifically experimentalists, with little introduction to computational biology and
60 bioinformatics. The ensuing content is structured such that it begins with some guidelines on
61 obtaining a gene's sequence, touches upon the experimental approaches for gene function
62 identification, and moves on to detail a number of useful computational approaches and tools for
63 functional annotation. It also sheds light on the most recent and exciting tools for functional
64 annotation based on artificial intelligence. Finally, it concludes with a comprehensive outlook
65 and research gaps for further work in the domain, that could be of use for developers and
66 bioinformaticians in general.

67 How to obtain a gene sequence?

68 Access to the gene repertoire of a plant species is usually gained through a transcriptome
69 assembly or a genome sequence. Given the large size of plant genomes and the large
70 proportion of non-genic elements, transcriptome assemblies have been a cost-effective way to
71 obtain protein encoding sequences of a species of interest (Haak *et al.* 2018). The rapid
72 technological development of long read sequencing made the generation of high quality
73 genome sequences affordable and feasible for many plant species (Marks *et al.* 2021; Pucker *et al.*
74 *et al.* 2022). Oxford Nanopore Technologies and Pacific Biosciences offer sequencing instruments
75 that enable the continuous sequencing of long DNA molecules with high raw read accuracy of
76 over 99%. The portability and affordable prices of ONT sequencers enable an ever increasing
77 number of scientists to actively participate in plant genomics (Pucker *et al.* 2022). Sequencing
78 data are often stored in FASTQ files that combine sequence and quality information (Cock *et al.*
79 2010). Long reads are processed by assemblers like HiCanu (Nurk *et al.* 2020), Flye
80 (Kolmogorov *et al.* 2019), Shasta (Shafin *et al.* 2020), or NextDenovo2 (GrandOmics 2023) to

81 produce highly continuous genome sequences. These assembled sequences are called contigs
82 and stored in a FASTA file (Lipman & Pearson 1985). Continuous sequences (contigs)
83 produced in the assembly process often represent chromosome arms or even entire
84 chromosomes in some cases. The quality and completeness of the assembled sequences can
85 be assessed with Merqury (Rhie *et al.* 2020) which checks the assembly for all k-mers that have
86 been observed in the reads. Most prominent in plant genomes are repeats and transposable
87 elements (TEs) that can be identified by tools like RepeatMasker (Smit *et al.* 2015), Extensive
88 de-novo TE Annotator (EDTA) (Ou *et al.* 2019), RepeatModeler2 (Flynn *et al.* 2020), or
89 TransposonUltimate (Riehl *et al.* 2022). When multiple genome sequences of a species are
90 investigated at the same time, panEDTA can be applied to benefit from the pangenome context
91 (Ou *et al.* 2022). As repeats, especially in the centromeres, become more accessible with long
92 reads, many studies are now investigating these parts of plant genomes (Naish *et al.* 2021;
93 Wlodzimierz *et al.* 2023). Excluding positions of repeats and transposable elements (TEs) in the
94 subsequent step of identifying protein-encoding plant genes is a common practice. This is done
95 to ensure that transposon genes are not included in the annotation, maintaining the accuracy of
96 the results. The gene prediction process can be performed by BRAKER3 (Gabriel *et al.* 2023),
97 GeMoMa (Keilwagen *et al.* 2016, 2019), CAT (Fiddes *et al.* 2018), or Funannotate (Palmer
98 2019) and results in gene models also known as structural annotation. Details about the
99 positions and structures of all genes are typically stored in a GFF3 file. While the
100 aforementioned tools predict only monocistronic gene models, OpenProt2021 supports
101 polycistronic gene models in the annotation of eukaryotic genome sequences (Brunet *et al.*
102 2021). While polycistronic genes have been described in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* (Gallaher
103 *et al.* 2021), there is currently limited information about the relevance of polycistronic genes in
104 land plants (García-Ríos *et al.* 1997; Wang *et al.* 2019). Some of these structural annotation
105 tools require RNA-seq reads from the target species or protein hints or gene models of a close
106 relative. RNA-seq reads are generated by sequencing fragments of cDNAs, which essentially
107 consist of concatenated exons without the intervening presence of introns. When aligned to a
108 genome sequence, gaps in the alignment of RNA-seq reads span the positions of introns.
109 Therefore, RNA-seq reads can reveal the exon/intron structure of a gene and indicate which
110 exons belong to the same gene. This process requires dedicated tools like STAR (Dobin *et al.*
111 2013; Dobin & Gingeras 2015) or HISAT2 (Kim *et al.* 2019), which can accurately split
112 alignments around introns. Reads derived from direct RNA sequencing or full length cDNA
113 sequencing enable the annotation of distinct transcript isoforms that can be the result of
114 alternative splicing (Amarasinghe *et al.* 2020; Guizard *et al.* 2023). Similarly, polypeptide
115 sequences from databases can be aligned to a genome sequence to inform the gene prediction
116 process. However, the inclusion of polypeptide sequence derived hints might lead to high rates
117 of false-positive predictions (Vuruputoor *et al.* 2023). These types of external information
118 already indicate a major limitation of today's gene prediction approaches: the structural
119 annotation is restricted to the transcribed region of a gene and does not cover the regulatory
120 elements in the promoter which would also be part of a plant gene. But in recent years, tools
121 based on deep learning have been developed that overcome the dependency on external hints.
122 Tiberius is one such novel deep-learning-based *ab initio* gene predictor (Gabriel *et al.* 2024). It
123 is aimed at eukaryotic gene prediction and its *ab initio* performance was shown to surpass that
124 of even BRAKER3 which uses external hints like RNA-seq reads and protein databases

125 (Gabriel *et al.* 2024). Helixer is another deep-learning-based structural annotator similar to
126 Tiberius, and offers a wide range of phylogenetic models including fungi, and can also be
127 applied to under-represented plant species (Holst *et al.* 2025). The completeness of a genome
128 sequence and the corresponding structural annotation can be assessed with BUSCO (Simão *et al.*
129 *et al.* 2015; Manni *et al.* 2021) that checks for the presence of highly conserved single copy genes.
130 The completeness reported by BUSCO for a genome sequence usually exceeds the reported
131 completeness reported for the corresponding annotation. This might be due to the inclusion of
132 pseudogenes in the completeness analysis of genome sequences, while gene prediction tools
133 would filter out such sequences. However, both values are often >95% suggesting that high
134 quality genomic resources are routinely generated and that missing genes are an exception. In
135 the gene prediction process, each gene receives a unique ID that enables access to all
136 information collected about this gene. As this ID is specific for a structural annotation, different
137 annotation versions and sources might use different IDs for the same biological entity. Matching
138 the IDs between different annotation versions is a frequent task that requires specific rules for
139 complicated cases where the annotation versions deviate substantially from each other. The
140 result of this process is a mapping table that connects each gene ID from one annotation
141 version to zero, one, or many IDs of another annotation version. Such mapping tables are
142 particularly important if many different annotation versions exist for the same species and are
143 used as reference by different research groups or consortia. An example would be *Vitis vinifera*,
144 for which a range of different reference genome sequences and annotation versions were
145 developed, sometimes in parallel by different groups, and favored by different parts of the
146 community (Velasco *et al.* 2007; Muñoz *et al.* 2014; Grimlet *et al.* 2014; Velt *et al.* 2023; Shi *et al.*
147 *et al.* 2023). It is important to enable the connection of biological insights reported in scientific
148 publications based on different annotation versions to integrate all knowledge in the body of
149 literature and to avoid redundant research endeavors. Another purpose of a gene ID is to
150 enable users to retrieve the underlying sequence together with any attached information from a
151 database. A practical solution to make genomic data accessible is a genome browser as
152 implemented in jbrowse (Buels *et al.* 2016; Diesh *et al.* 2023) or gbrowse (Stein 2013). A
153 graphical user interface and access via the internet enable users to retrieve the desired
154 sequences of a gene of interest. Famous examples are The Arabidopsis Information Resource
155 (TAIR) (Lamesch *et al.* 2012; Berardini *et al.* 2015), Banana Genome Hub (Droc *et al.* 2022),
156 Sol Genomics Network (Fernandez-Pozo *et al.* 2015), and Coffee Genome Hub (Dereeper *et al.*
157 2015) that also provide additional information besides gene and genome sequences.
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Figure 1: Simplified workflow showing the major steps of a plant genomics project leading to a genome sequence and corresponding annotation that can be accessed through a genome browser.

164 How to understand the function of a gene?

165 The classical reverse genetics approaches towards gene function elucidation are studying a
166 knock-out or overexpression line. As a targeted integration of DNA into the plant genome
167 through homologous recombination is not feasible, researchers had to rely on randomly
168 introduced mutations during the last decades. Large collections of knock-out lines were
169 established for model organisms like *Arabidopsis thaliana* (SALK, GABI-Kat) (Alonso *et al.*
170 2003; Rosso *et al.* 2003; O'Malley *et al.* 2015). These lines are based on a random integration
171 of T-DNAs into the plant genome and a localization of the integration site in the genome (Rosso
172 *et al.* 2003; Kleinboelting *et al.* 2012). Scientists can order a knock-out line that harbors a T-
173 DNA inside their gene of interest through the NASC and ABRC. The floral dip method, which
174 involves a *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*-mediated transfer of DNA into generative *A. thaliana*
175 cells (Clough & Bent 1998), has been a frequently applied method to generate stable transgenic
176 lines. A careful characterization of T-DNA insertion lines is necessary as multiple T-DNA copies
177 might affect different genes and can also trigger large-scale genomic rearrangements (Pucker *et al.*
178 2021). T-DNA based integration of genes into mutant lines can also serve as a method to
179 characterize genes of non-model organisms in *A. thaliana* through complementation
180 experiments (Lee *et al.* 2013; Schilbert *et al.* 2021; Aslam *et al.* 2022). The development of
181 different CRISPR-Cas9-derived systems enables plant biologists to generate mutants in a
182 targeted way (Grützner *et al.* 2021). However, this still requires the transformation of plants with
183 the necessary constructs and a following validation of the introduced genomic changes. A gene
184 knock-out is not possible for essential genes as their loss would be lethal. This makes knock-
185 down a powerful alternative strategy. Initially triggered by chance in *Petunia* engineering
186 experiments (Napoli *et al.* 1990), knock-down, i.e. reduction of transcript abundance, developed
187 into a strategy in functional plant genomics (Samuilov *et al.* 2018; Debladis *et al.* 2020; Demirer
188 & Landry 2021). Virus-induced gene silencing (VIGS) emerged as a convenient tool to also
189 knock-down genes in non-model organisms (Ruiz *et al.* 1998; Lu *et al.* 2003; Dommes *et al.*
190 2019).

191
192 Forward genetics is the opposite approach that can reveal the gene responsible for a certain
193 phenotype. Frequently deployed methods to identify causal genes are genome-wide association
194 studies (GWAS) (Lee & Lee 2021; Gloss *et al.* 2022) and mapping-by-sequencing (MBS)
195 (Schneeberger & Weigel 2011; James *et al.* 2013) followed by an in-depth investigation of an
196 identified quantitative trait locus (QTL). The concept of these approaches is to find systematic
197 genetic differences between two groups of individuals that have been pooled based on their
198 phenotype. These systematic genetic differences can be small sequence variants or
199 presence/absence variants affecting entire genes. Tools like SnpEff (Cingolani *et al.* 2012) and
200 NAVIP (Baasner *et al.* 2025) enable a prediction of the functional consequences of a sequence
201 variant. GWAS and MBS have been deployed to study *A. thaliana* gene functions and to provide
202 insights into crop genes determining important traits (Mascher *et al.* 2014; Sasaki *et al.* 2021;
203 Schilbert *et al.* 2022; Naake *et al.* 2023; Sielemann *et al.* 2023).

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 208 **Figure 2:** Schematic illustration of forward and reverse genetics. Forward genetics starts from
 209 the phenotype and identifies the underlying genotype. Reverse genetics starts from the
 210 genotype and aims to understand the resulting phenotype.
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212 **How to understand the function of all genes in a genome?**

213 The gene function elucidation approaches described above suffer from poor scalability and are
 214 therefore not suitable for investigation of all gene functions in a newly sequenced plant genome.
 215 These have two major disadvantages: they are time intensive and costly. This restricts the
 216 investigation of gene functions through knock-out, overexpression, or knock-down lines to small
 217 numbers of genes and a small number of genetically accessible species. Given that a
 218 substantial amount of information about genes and their functions is already available in
 219 databases, individual users can access this through sequence comparison. This cross-species
 220 annotation transfer is based on the assumption that similar sequences have similar functions.
 221 While this holds true in most cases, some very similar sequences, paralogs, can differ in their
 222 function. It is generally assumed that only orthologs, i.e. the same gene in different species, are
 223 highly likely to harbor the same function (Eisen 1998). The major challenge in functional
 224 annotation is therefore the reliable and efficient identification of orthologs i.e. to clearly
 225 distinguish between orthologs ,paralogs, and in some cases xenologs. Five conceptually
 226 different types of analyses can be distinguished that allow the connection of genes between
 227 species. The first type utilizes only the sequence of a gene or the derived polypeptide sequence
 228 for basic similarity analyses. The second type performs a phylogenetic analysis to place the
 229 sequence of interest in an evolutionary context with similar sequences. The third type screens
 230 for genomic regions where a number of flanking genes, not just the gene of interest, show
 231 similarity between two species. This approach utilizes information beyond the borders of the
 232 gene itself to establish a more reliable pair of orthologs. The fourth type involves the use of

233 protein structures to facilitate functional annotation and is becoming more scalable with the
234 rapid advancements in protein structure prediction and modelling (Rennie & Oliver 2025). The
235 last type of analysis leverages gene expression data that can be used to perform coexpression
236 analysis amongst genes in a genome, and thus aids in understanding the gene function (Grünig
237 & Pucker 2025). Here again, strides in machine learning have enabled cross-species transfer of
238 the information through graph and network-based algorithms (Li *et al.* 2023).
239

240 Gene sequence similarity analyses

241 Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) is the most frequently used tool in life sciences and
242 enables a quick comparison of a sequence against a comprehensive database (Altschul *et al.*
243 1990, 1997). The availability of BLAST through websites hosted by the NCBI, Phytozome
244 (Goodstein *et al.* 2012), or TAIR (Lamesch *et al.* 2012; Berardini *et al.* 2015) enables life
245 scientists to explore a gene function without computational biology skills. Annotation terms
246 associated with the best BLAST hits can give a first impression about the function of the gene of
247 interest. There is a large number of databases that contain valuable information about sequence
248 functions. Examples are Plant Reactome (Naithani *et al.* 2020), MetaCyc (Caspi *et al.* 2020),
249 Gene Ontology (GO) (Ashburner *et al.* 2000; Gene Ontology Consortium 2021), Protein family
250 (Pfam) (Mistry *et al.* 2021), Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) (Kanehisa &
251 Goto 2000; Kanehisa *et al.* 2023), and the large collection of sequences hosted by the
252 International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration, a consortium formed by GenBank,
253 ENA, and DDBJ (Clark *et al.* 2016; Sayers *et al.* 2020; Arita *et al.* 2021). There are specific tools
254 that can assign information of these databases to polypeptide sequences derived from a novel
255 genome sequence. Examples are BLAST2GO (Conesa *et al.* 2005) that attaches GO terms and
256 KAAS (Moriya *et al.* 2007) that assigns KEGG identifiers to sequences. InterProScan5 (Jones *et al.*
257 2014) assigns a range of different identifiers to novel polypeptide sequences including GO
258 terms, KEGG identifier, Pfams, and PANTHER annotation terms. Mercator4 (Lohse *et al.* 2014)
259 is available as a web service and can efficiently annotate provided polypeptide sequences by
260 assigning them to clusters of similar sequences. BLAST is one of the most frequently used tools
261 for the identification of similar sequences, but it is not a reliable method to identify orthologs,
262 because only small stretches of highly similar sequences are considered for the alignment
263 (Altschul *et al.* 1990). The chances of identifying *bona fide* orthologs can be increased by
264 performing a reciprocal best BLAST hit analysis, which adds an additional filter layer (Pucker *et al.*
265 2016). Comparing all polypeptide sequences of a species against another species or even
266 an entire database has huge computational costs and can result in long run times. Such tasks
267 usually require a parallel analysis of sequences in batches on a high performance compute
268 cluster. A faster BLAST alternative is DIAMOND (Buchfink *et al.* 2015, 2021), but this speed
269 increase comes at the expense of higher memory consumption. If a large number of sequences
270 needs to be compared against a database, users might want to use DIAMOND instead of
271 BLAST. Eukaryotic Non-Model Transcriptome Annotation Pipeline (ENTAP) is a dedicated tool
272 for the functional annotation of transcriptome assembly sequences through comparison against
273 several databases (Hart *et al.* 2020). There are also dedicated tools for the identification of
274 orthologs. JustOrthologs identifies putative orthologs through characteristics like gene structure,
275 CDS length, and dinucleotide percentages in a computationally efficient way (Miller *et al.* 2019).

276 SwiftOrtho is a graph-based tool for the identification of orthologs that was also developed with
277 a focus on minimizing the computational costs (Hu & Friedberg 2019). Since there are often not
278 1:1-relationships between species, a number of orthologous sequences must be collected in an
279 orthogroup. OrthoFinder2 (Emms & Kelly 2019) enables an automatic identification of
280 orthogroups based on a number of polypeptide sequence sets belonging to different species. An
281 advantage of this analysis is the ability to integrate polypeptide sequences derived from *de novo*
282 transcriptome assemblies or short read-based genome sequence assemblies. Unfortunately,
283 orthogroups might be too large and consequently not helpful in many scenarios where large
284 gene families are of interest. Examples are the large transcription factor gene families MYB and
285 bHLH that can have >100 members per plant species (Stracke *et al.* 2001; Zimmermann *et al.*
286 2004; Dubos *et al.* 2010; Thoben & Pucker 2023) and are often clustered into a small number of
287 orthogroups. As members of these gene families belong to dozens of subgroups that have
288 individual functions (Dubos *et al.* 2010; Pucker, Pandey, *et al.* 2020), a fine separation is
289 required for accurate functional annotation transfer.
290

291 Phylogenetic analyses

292 The construction of phylogenetic trees has been reported to be more accurate when predicting
293 protein functions than the application of basic sequence similarity analyses, because they
294 enable a more reliable identification of orthologs (Eisen 1998; Sjölander 2004; Brown &
295 Sjölander 2006; Pucker, Reiher, *et al.* 2020). While other studies suggest that the inclusion of
296 paralogs improves the accuracy in some pairwise comparisons (Nehrt *et al.* 2011; Stamboulian
297 *et al.* 2020), an accurate assignment of homologous sequences across species forms the basis
298 of the annotation transfer.
299

300 There have been quite a number of tools developed for phylogenetic tree building. A well known
301 and frequently used tree building software is IQ-TREE 3 (Wong *et al.* 2025). IQ-TREE 3 offers a
302 number of features along with the integration of the ModelFinder algorithm for automatic
303 substitution model selection for a more accurate phylogenetic estimation (Kalyaanamoorthy *et*
304 *al.* 2017). FastTree (Price *et al.* 2010) is another popular tree building tool that is extremely fast
305 when compared to IQ-TREE 3. It can scale up well for a large scale analysis while giving reliable
306 estimates, although they might not be of the high accuracy obtained with IQ-TREE3. These
307 softwares and methods have been utilized to create phylogenetic databases and have also
308 been integrated in a number of computational tools.
309

310 Databases like Phytozome (Goodstein *et al.* 2012), PANTHER (Thomas *et al.* 2022), OMA
311 (Altenhoff *et al.* 2024), PhylomeDB (Fuentes *et al.* 2022), GreenPhyIDB (Guignon *et al.* 2021),
312 or OrthoDB (Kuznetsov *et al.* 2023) provide the phylogenetic relationships of all sequences
313 belonging to the included organisms. Specific advantages and details about the underlying tools
314 for the generation of many of these resources have been recently reviewed (de Boissier &
315 Habermann 2020). These phylogenies can be utilized to transfer annotation information
316 between the included species, but would require additional processing to obtain a functional
317 annotation file for a species of interest. A comprehensive and up-to-date API documentation

318 facilitates the efficient utilization of these databases. Unfortunately, the representation of plant
319 species in these databases is generally sparse.

320
321 Many computational tools can be run locally to compare sequence data sets with the objective
322 of reliable ortholog identification for the following annotation transfer. A phylogeny-based
323 analysis of all candidates enables an accurate annotation of members belonging to large gene
324 families like MYBs and bHLHs (Pucker 2022; Thoben & Pucker 2023). The eggNOG-mapper v2
325 can functionally annotate all predicted polypeptide sequences of a new species through
326 comparison against a large collection of previously computed orthogroups, the eggNOG
327 database (Huerta-Cepas *et al.* 2019; Cantalapiedra *et al.* 2021). Unfortunately, this database
328 does only contain a very limited number of plant datasets yet (Huerta-Cepas *et al.* 2019).
329 Recently, SHOOT (Emms & Kelly 2022) was released as a phylogenetics-informed alternative
330 to BLAST. While the assignment of orthologs would be more reliable through SHOOT, it does
331 not cover the entire dataset accessible through the NCBI-hosted BLAST web service.
332 PharaohFUN assigns functional annotation information to supplied sequences based on gene
333 trees and a data set covering a wide taxonomic diversity of plants (Ramos-González *et al.*
334 2023). FastOMA is another tool that was developed to efficiently identify orthologs in huge
335 datasets that will be produced by the rapid generation of complete genome sequences
336 (Majidian, Nevers, *et al.* 2025). FastOMA also helps understand 1:1 and m:n relationships
337 between orthologs and is available for use as a web interface as well as locally installable
338 software. Users might want to inspect the intermediate results that lead to the annotation of
339 selected genes. If phylogenetic trees are generated as intermediate files by the above
340 mentioned tools, these can be visualized in iTOL (Letunic & Bork 2021). PhyloProfile (Tran *et al.*
341 2018) also enables users to visualize phylogenetic information associated with a gene and
342 could provide another starting point for the manual inspection of selected cases. While online
343 tools like PhyloFacts (Krishnamurthy *et al.* 2006) or OrthoVenn2 (Xu *et al.* 2019) could make the
344 functional annotation process convenient, the throughput is often limited and the risk of
345 becoming inaccessible due to broken links in the original publication is huge.

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348 Synteny analyses

349 An annotation transfer solution with very high resolution is the identification of syntelogs, i.e.
350 genes that are located at the same genomic position (Lyons *et al.* 2008). This approach relies
351 on synteny i.e. the order of genes being roughly the same in the compared plant genomes. As
352 the order and orientation of genes is changing during evolution, this approach is limited to the
353 comparison of species within a certain phylogenetic distance. The simultaneous analysis of
354 multiple neighboring genes enables a more specific assignment of orthologs across species
355 borders by including information outside the gene of interest. Tools for a synteny analysis are
356 MCscan/JCVI (Tang *et al.* 2008, 2024), TBtools-II (Chen *et al.* 2023), TOGA (Kirilenko *et al.*
357 2023), OrthoRefine (Ludwig & Mrázek 2024), and SOI (Zhang *et al.* 2025). Synteny analyses
358 are an excellent way to identify orthologs with high reliability and resolution, but the
359 computational costs exceed those of a simple analysis via BLAST (**Figure 3**).

360

361
 362 **Figure 3:** Methods for the high-throughput assignment of functional annotation to novel genes.
 363 Different concepts can be distinguished: (1) analysis of basic sequence similarity, (2) analysis in
 364 phylogenetic context, (3) analysis of synteny, (4) protein structure, (5) gene expression, or (6)

365 combined approaches. The listed tools are only examples. See GitHub repository
366 <https://github.com/PuckerLab/FunctionalAnnotation> for an extended list of tools for the functional
367 annotation.
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370 Protein structure analyses

371 If the structure of two proteins is similar, the function might be similar too. Protein structures are
372 conserved to a greater extent than amino acid sequences since they determine the biochemical
373 functions of the protein. Despite varying phylogenetic distances and levels of sequence
374 divergence, protein structure can serve as a strong signal for functional similarity, making it a
375 powerful functional annotation method (Borujeni & Salavati 2024). But the quality of knowledge
376 about protein structures was a huge challenge until the last decade. With the release of
377 AlphaFold, a deep learning-based algorithm for protein structure prediction with an accuracy
378 comparable to that of experimental methods, this challenge has been overcome to a great
379 extent (Jumper *et al.* 2021). As a result, the Protein Data Bank database (Berman *et al.* 2000),
380 and other prominent protein structure databases like AlphaFoldDB database (Varadi *et al.* 2022)
381 are witnessing an exponential increase in the number of high quality protein structure models.
382 To find protein structure matches in these vast databases, a number of tools are also available.
383 The Dali web server is a well known resource for structural comparison of proteins (Holm 2022).
384 Foldseek is a recently released protein structure alignment tool that is computationally efficient
385 and has very low computational costs when compared to other protein structure alignment tools.
386 It searches across AlphaFoldDB and PDB for protein structure matches of query proteins, and is
387 available as a webserver and also as a tool for local installation (van Kempen *et al.* 2024).
388 Understanding protein function based on physicochemical properties extrapolated from the
389 structure is the next immediate step in functional analysis. But this is manually time consuming
390 and interfacing between structure metadata formats from the different databases is complex. To
391 automate this step, ProCaliper, a Python library, was recently released. It can interface with
392 UniProt (Apweiler *et al.* 2004), AlphaFoldDB and also take in files in the PDB format, and
393 provide in-depth residue-level annotations. Thus structure-based clustering of proteins has the
394 ability to discover novel protein families (Durairaj *et al.* 2023) and tackle difficult cases where
395 sequence similarity-based methods cannot be applied effectively (Yu *et al.* 2025). Additionally,
396 protein-protein interaction information can also help to understand the function of a protein
397 encoding gene.
398

399 Expression analyses

400 A gene has to be expressed at the right time and place to be functional and for its transcript
401 abundance to be estimated. This makes gene expression data extremely useful for
402 understanding gene function (Julca *et al.* 2023; Grünig & Pucker 2025). Several different
403 transcriptome-based methods can be used for functional annotation. Transcriptomic data sets
404 can be powerful resources to connect a candidate gene to members of a co-expression network
405 if no information about any orthologs is available. JGI Plant Gene Atlas is a prime example of

406 utilizing gene expression data to assign functional information to uncharacterized sequences
407 (Sreedasyam *et al.* 2023). Coexpression networks conserved across species borders and
408 characteristic responses of gene expression to stress treatments can be informative
409 (Sreedasyam *et al.* 2023). As the resource can be updated continuously in the future, relevance
410 will gain as more data becomes available. Well established tools to perform a co-expression
411 analysis locally are WGCNA (Langfelder & Horvath 2008) and GENIE3 (Huynh-Thu *et al.*
412 2010)/dynGENIE3 (Huynh-Thu & Geurts 2018). These tools would require count tables that
413 contain information about the activity of all genes. Downloading all RNA-seq datasets of a
414 species and processing them is computationally intensive. Precomputed datasets might be
415 available through Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) (Barrett *et al.* 2013), which does collect
416 some preprocessed datasets in addition to the raw RNA-seq reads. Additionally, several studies
417 released the pre-processed expression datasets (Hadish 2023; Grünig & Pucker 2025;
418 Choudhary *et al.* 2026). These can serve as excellent resources for data re-use and support big
419 data analyses in the life sciences domain. Once a co-expression network is constructed by any
420 of the above mentioned tools, Cytoscape (Shannon *et al.* 2003) could be utilized to visualize the
421 network for manual in-depth inspection. Connecting gene expression data to other omics or
422 phenotypic data can also support the functional annotation process (Singh *et al.* 2022). Genes
423 associated with a specific metabolite or a particular trait can be identified in this way. Examples
424 are the discovery of the podophyllotoxin biosynthesis pathway in *Podophyllum hexandrum* (Lau
425 & Sattely 2015) or the montbretin A biosynthesis pathway in *Crococsmia x crocosmiiflora*
426 (Irmisch *et al.* 2018, 2019). It is important to follow-up on these connections to distinguish
427 between correlation and causation in these cases. Further, the genes mined in individual
428 species with coexpression network analysis can be used for comparative transcriptomics across
429 species (Grünig & Pucker 2025). This involves multiple pairwise gene set comparisons or
430 hierarchical clustering techniques, and homolog assessment through metrics like the Jaccard
431 Index, that can identify gene expression-based homologs from the clusters (Julca *et al.* 2023).
432

433 Combined approaches

434 An optimal way forward is to combine the approaches and leverage the synergy of their
435 individual merits for functional annotation transfer. For instance, sequence similarity-based
436 approaches help get a good number of initial ortholog candidates. Next, when methods like
437 phylogeny are employed on these candidates, it would result in a list of orthologs that have
438 passed through these multiple approaches and are hence more confident and accurate. Some
439 tools exemplifying this approach have been developed for automatic annotation of the large
440 transcription factor (TF) families of MYBs and bHLHs in plants (Pucker 2022; Thoben & Pucker
441 2023). These tools combine sequence similarity searches with well-known candidates of the
442 TFs along with phylogeny to annotate these sequences in novel plant genome sequences.
443 DupyliCate (Natarajan & Pucker 2025) is another tool for gene duplication identification,
444 classification and further analysis, which can integrate gene expression data for assessing the
445 expression divergence. Next, Functional Annotations using Sequence and Structure Orthology
446 (FASSO) (Andorf *et al.* 2022) is another tool that combines the reciprocal best hit approach
447 based on sequence similarity and structural similarity to find orthologs. It also gives confidence
448 scores for the identified orthologs and also helps find existing mis-annotations. CoExpPhylo

449 (Grünig & Pucker 2025) automates the identification of genes co-expressed in a specific
450 pathway and across multiple species. CoExpPhylo uses phylogeny as a filter to avoid false-
451 positives that frequently show up in coexpression studies.

452 Looking across domains - xenologs and functional annotation

453 Xenologs are genes that are transferred between organisms through mechanisms other than
454 reproduction and can occur across all the domains of life. A successful horizontal gene transfer
455 (HGT) event necessitates transfer of genetic elements from the donor to the recipient crossing
456 the multiple organismal and cellular barriers on the way. Depending on the integration of the
457 foreign DNA in the vegetative or reproductive tissues of the recipient, the inter-generational
458 transfer of xenologs and their propagation to the progeny is facilitated. Xenologs have been
459 reported to have roles in stress tolerance and adaptation functions (Kamal *et al.* 2021). While
460 HGTs are commonly reported between bacteria and plant- bacteria, plant-plant, plant-fungi,
461 plant-insect, and plant-virus transfers have also been discovered (Azad *et al.* 2025). Sequence
462 similarity comparisons, codon-usage bias, and phylogenetic incongruence are some methods
463 used to identify HGT events (Mariault *et al.* 2025). However, amelioration or adaptation of the
464 xenolog to the host genome, makes the identification of xenologs challenging. Moreover, a
465 xenolog can undergo gene duplication, and can have many fates like sub-functionalization, and
466 neo-functionalization or could be pseudogenized and undergo gene loss, in which case it would
467 not be detected. These factors make its functional annotation and evolutionary trajectory hard to
468 determine (Treangen & Rocha 2011). Tools like Notung (Darby *et al.* 2017) have been
469 developed to identify xenologs, characterize any gene duplication events in their evolutionary
470 trajectory and integrate phylogenetic reconciliation approaches for gene function elucidation.
471 This was majorly applied and tested on prokaryotic genomes. CoreCruncher (Harris *et al.* 2021)
472 is another software that helps uncover orthologs, paralogs, xenologs, and partially and
473 completely hidden paralogs and xenologs across a large set of prokaryotic genomes. But there
474 are no concrete tools or methods developed for catching HGT events outside the prokaryotes'
475 domains, making it an interesting research gap with multiple exciting possibilities for developers
476 in the future. A recent study found that a number of previously reported HGT events could be
477 attributed to alternative explanations like gene loss or different taxon selections for the
478 phylogeny analysis, reinstating the need for better tools for xenolog identification (Aguirre-
479 Carvajal & Armijos-Jaramillo 2025).

480

481 How can artificial intelligence improve the functional annotation 482 process?

483 One major challenge in genomics is the efficient exploitation of available data sets for the
484 annotation of novel sequences. Various sequence databases show an exponential growth,
485 which provides an excellent resource for data reuse (Sielemann *et al.* 2020; Marks *et al.* 2021).
486 Simultaneously, it is also feasible and rewarding to automate processes that have been
487 performed by human experts during the last years, e.g. the annotation of enzyme sequences.
488 This increases reproducibility and allows scale-up of annotation processes. One example is

489 Knowledge-based Identification of Pathway Enzymes (KIPes) that automates all steps a
490 researcher would conduct when exploring biosynthesis genes of a generally well-known
491 pathway in a novel species (Pucker, Reiher, *et al.* 2020; Rempel *et al.* 2023). This
492 implementation of analysis steps needs to be combined with expert knowledge about the
493 pathway of interest. When investigating enzymes, details about the functionally important amino
494 acid residues (in the active center) could be a valuable source of information to predict whether
495 an enzyme is active (Pucker, Reiher, *et al.* 2020). So far, this requires an extensive body of
496 literature about the pathway of interest, which is only available for widespread pathways like the
497 flavonoid biosynthesis (Pucker, Reiher, *et al.* 2020) or the carotenoid biosynthesis (Rempel *et*
498 *al.* 2023). With increasing data availability, more pathways will be accessible through automatic
499 processes. Also, literature research had to be done manually during the last years, but current
500 artificial intelligence (AI) developments might enable automatic screening of publications in the
501 near future (de la Torre-López *et al.* 2023). Open access publishing and the release of scientific
502 publication in machine readable formats will pave the way to a more comprehensive cross-
503 species transfer of knowledge. Whenever expert behavior can be described by clear rules and
504 is not relying on 'gut feeling', an automation is feasible. Harnessing the full power of the
505 scientific literature for upcoming annotation projects holds great promise.

506
507 Large language models (LLMs) are useful in constructing annotation text that is easily
508 accessible by humans. Given the amount of annotation terms that can be retrieved from various
509 databases, generating a concise and accurate string of human-readable information is a major
510 challenge. While tools like InterProScan5 (Jones *et al.* 2014) already compile a set of annotation
511 details based on different databases, the tabular output requires re-structuring for readability.
512 Previously, many annotation terms were stored as English words, but LLMs could easily enable
513 multi language support. Generating more detailed annotation information by processing all of
514 the available literature is another approach to advance gene function understanding. Databases
515 connecting important pieces of information from scientific articles to genes are crucial functional
516 genomics. The most striking example is TAIR that was built by experts curating the data (Huala
517 *et al.* 2001; Lamesch *et al.* 2012; Berardini *et al.* 2015). Recently, PlantConnectome was
518 constructed by screening over 100,000 abstracts of plant biology publications for information
519 about the functions of genes (Fo *et al.* 2023). With the advances in generative modelling and AI,
520 LLMs tailored for tackling tasks relevant to plant genomics have been unveiled. DeepPGDB is
521 one such AI-based interactive genomic database (Li *et al.* 2025). It contains over fifty plant
522 genome sequences of high quality and enables the user to do a wide range of tasks from simple
523 text-based queries to generating specific tool commands and other bioinformatics workflows like
524 sequence retrieval, alignment, and visualization (Li *et al.* 2025). Such innovations just indicate
525 the cusp of the immense possibilities and tools that can be developed to further tackle the
526 functional annotation challenge with the power of artificial intelligence and machine learning.
527 While the innovation potential of LLMs is enormous, there are also potential risks like the
528 requirement for appropriate filtering when collecting the database or ensuring the accuracy of
529 generated output. A particular challenge is the avoidance of circular conclusions when research
530 data generated with LLMs serves as a basis for the development of future LLMs. Further,
531 imbalanced representation of plant species, with data being abundant only for model plants like
532 *A. thaliana* or *Z. mays*, is a data-centric issue relevant to the deployment of machine learning

533 (ML) approaches for plant functional annotation. Moreover, the heterogeneous nature of
534 biological data is a challenge that needs to be tackled upfront for fully embracing the benefits of
535 ML algorithms in the plant science community.

536
537 Functional annotation in itself can be split into small pieces of a large puzzle like enzymatic
538 function, gene expression regulation, protein structural information, protein localization, protein-
539 protein interactions, that come together to give a biological functional interpretation. Each of
540 these different segments of functional annotation have the capability to be handled as
541 mathematical problems that can be solved with either supervised or unsupervised ML models to
542 obtain good results with large throughput (Mahood *et al.* 2020). JASPAR 2026 is a concrete
543 example of such an approach that has integrated deep learning and offers predictions and
544 information of about 1000 transcription factor profiles of plants (Ovek Baydar *et al.* 2025).

545 **Summary**

546 Rapid development of long read sequencing technologies over the last years have enabled an
547 almost routine generation of high quality genome sequences and structural annotations. The
548 major bottleneck is currently the elucidation of gene functions. A range of different approaches
549 including sequence similarity, synteny, and phylogeny transfer knowledge between orthologs
550 across species borders. With breakthroughs in protein structure prediction, protein structures
551 can serve as strong signatures for functional analyses. Large transcriptomic resources enable a
552 reference-independent assignment of novel genes to biosynthesis pathways or processes
553 based on comprehensive co-expression analyses. In the future, additional connections with
554 other omics datasets could establish novel annotation approaches.

555

556 **Declarations**

557 **Availability of data and materials**

558 This manuscript is supported by a more detailed description of various tools for the functional
559 annotation of plant sequences available on GitHub
560 (<https://github.com/PuckerLab/FunctionalAnnotation>).

561

562 **Competing interests**

563 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

564

565 Authors' contributions

566 BP planned the study. SN and BP wrote the manuscript. MH, and BP designed the figures. All
567 authors have read the final version of the manuscript and approved its submission.

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572 have been retrieved from bioicons.com: (1) Protein_colored icon by DBCLS
573 <https://togotv.dbcls.jp/en/pics.html> is licensed under CC-BY 4.0 Unported
574 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> and (2) heatmap icon by ChenxinLi
575 <https://twitter.com/ChenxinLi2> is licensed under CC-BY 4.0 Unported
576 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

577 References

- 578 Aguirre-Carvajal Kevin, Armijos-Jaramillo Vinicio (2025) Reassessing Interkingdom
579 Horizontal Gene Transfer Suggests Limited Influence on Plant Genomes. *Ecology and*
580 *Evolution* **15**:e72653.
- 581 Alonso José M., Stepanova Anna N., Leisse Thomas J., Kim Christopher J., Chen
582 Huaming, Shinn Paul, Stevenson Denise K., Zimmerman Justin, Barajas P., Cheuk R.,
583 Gadrinab C., Heller C., Jeske A., Koesema E., Meyers C.C., Parker H., Prednis L.,
584 Ansari Y., Choy N., Deen H., Geralt M., Hazari N., Hom E., Karnes M., Mulholland C.,
585 Ndubaku R., Schmidt I., Guzman P., Aguilar-Henonin L., Schmid M., Weigel D., Carter
586 D.E., Marchand T., Risseeuw E., Brogden D., Zeko A., Crosby W.L., Berry C.C., Ecker
587 J.R. (2003) Genome-wide insertional mutagenesis of *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Science*
588 (New York, NY) **301**:653–657.
- 589 Altenhoff A.M., Warwick Vesztröcy A., Bernard C., Train C.-M., Nicheperovich A.,
590 Prieto Baños S., Julca I., Moi D., Nevers Y., Majidian S., Dessimoz C., Glover N.M.
591 (2024) OMA orthology in 2024: improved prokaryote coverage, ancestral and extant GO
592 enrichment, a revamped synteny viewer and more in the OMA Ecosystem. *Nucleic Acids*
593 *Research* **52**:D513–D521.
- 594 Altschul S.F., Gish W., Miller W., Myers E.W., Lipman D.J. (1990) Basic local alignment
595 search tool. *Journal of Molecular Biology* **215**:403–410.
- 596 Altschul S.F., Madden T.L., Schäffer A.A., Zhang J., Zhang Z., Miller W., Lipman D.J.
597 (1997) Gapped BLAST and PSI-BLAST: a new generation of protein database search
598 programs. *Nucleic Acids Research* **25**:3389–3402.
- 599 Amarasinghe S.L., Su S., Dong X., Zappia L., Ritchie M.E., Gouil Q. (2020)
600 Opportunities and challenges in long-read sequencing data analysis. *Genome Biology*
601 **21**:30.

602 Andorf C.M., Sen S., Hayford R.K., Portwood J.L., Cannon E.K., Harper L.C., Gardiner
603 J.M., Sen T.Z., Woodhouse M.R. (2022) FASSO: An AlphaFold based method to assign
604 functional annotations by combining sequence and structure orthology.
605 :2022.11.10.516002. [online] URL:
606 <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2022.11.10.516002v1> (accessed 14 January
607 2024).

608 Apweiler R., Bairoch A., Wu C.H., Barker W.C., Boeckmann B., Ferro S., Gasteiger E.,
609 Huang H., Lopez R., Magrane M., Martin M.J., Natale D.A., O'Donovan C., Redaschi N.,
610 Yeh L.L. (2004) UniProt: the Universal Protein knowledgebase. *Nucleic Acids Research*
611 **32**:D115–D119.

612 Arita M., Karsch-Mizrachi I., Cochrane G., on behalf of the International Nucleotide
613 Sequence Database Collaboration (2021) The international nucleotide sequence
614 database collaboration. *Nucleic Acids Research* **49**:D121–D124.

615 Ashburner M., Ball C.A., Blake J.A., Botstein D., Butler H., Cherry J.M., Davis A.P.,
616 Dolinski K., Dwight S.S., Eppig J.T., Harris M.A., Hill D.P., Issel-Tarver L., Kasarskis A.,
617 Lewis S., Matese J.C., Richardson J.E., Ringwald M., Rubin G.M., Sherlock G. (2000)
618 Gene Ontology: tool for the unification of biology. *Nature Genetics* **25**:25–29.

619 Aslam M., She Z., Jakada B.H., Fakher B., Greaves J.G., Yan M., Chen Y., Zheng P.,
620 Cheng Y., Qin Y. (2022) Interspecific complementation-restoration of phenotype in
621 *Arabidopsis cuc2cuc3* mutant by sugarcane CUC2 gene. *BMC Plant Biology* **22**:47.

622 Azad R.B., Kasfy S.H., Molla K., Islam T. (2025) Horizontal Gene Transfer in Plants and
623 Implications for Biotechnology. *Plant-Environment Interactions* **6**:e70087.

624 Baasner J.-S., Rempel A., Howard D., Pucker B. (2025) NAVIP: Unraveling the influence
625 of neighboring small sequence variants on functional impact prediction. *PLOS*
626 *Computational Biology* **21**:e1012732.

627 Barrett T., Wilhite S.E., Ledoux P., Evangelista C., Kim I.F., Tomashevsky M., Marshall
628 K.A., Phillippy K.H., Sherman P.M., Holko M., Yefanov A., Lee H., Zhang N., Robertson
629 C.L., Serova N., Davis S., Soboleva A. (2013) NCBI GEO: archive for functional
630 genomics data sets—update. *Nucleic Acids Research* **41**:D991–D995.

631 Berardini T.Z., Mundodi S., Reiser L., Huala E., Garcia-Hernandez M., Zhang P., Mueller
632 L.A., Yoon J., Doyle A., Lander G., Moseyko N., Yoo D., Xu I., Zoeckler B., Montoya M.,
633 Miller N., Weems D., Rhee S.Y. (2004) Functional Annotation of the Arabidopsis
634 Genome Using Controlled Vocabularies. *Plant Physiology* **135**:745–755.

635 Berardini T.Z., Reiser L., Li D., Mezheritsky Y., Muller R., Strait E., Huala E. (2015) The
636 arabidopsis information resource: Making and mining the “gold standard” annotated
637 reference plant genome. *genus* **53**:474–485.

638 Berman H.M., Westbrook J., Feng Z., Gilliland G., Bhat T.N., Weissig H., Shindyalov
639 I.N., Bourne P.E. (2000) The Protein Data Bank. *Nucleic Acids Research* **28**:235–242.

640 de Boissier P., Habermann B.H. (2020) A Practical Guide to Orthology Resources. In:
641 Pontarotti P (ed) *Evolutionary Biology—A Transdisciplinary Approach*. Springer

642 International Publishing, Cham, pp 41–77. [online] URL: [https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-57246-4_3)
643 030-57246-4_3 (accessed 14 January 2024).

644 Borujeni P.M., Salavati R. (2024) Functional domain annotation by structural similarity.
645 NAR Genomics and Bioinformatics **6**:lqae005.

646 Brown D., Sjölander K. (2006) Functional Classification Using Phylogenomic Inference.
647 PLOS Computational Biology **2**:e77.

648 Brunet M.A., Lucier J.-F., Levesque M., Leblanc S., Jacques J.-F., Al-Saedi H.R.H.,
649 Guilloy N., Grenier F., Avino M., Fournier I., Salzet M., Ouangraoua A., Scott M.S.,
650 Boisvert F.-M., Roucou X. (2021) OpenProt 2021: deeper functional annotation of the
651 coding potential of eukaryotic genomes. Nucleic Acids Research **49**:D380–D388.

652 Buchfink B., Reuter K., Drost H.-G. (2021) Sensitive protein alignments at tree-of-life
653 scale using DIAMOND. Nature Methods **18**:366–368.

654 Buchfink B., Xie C., Huson D.H. (2015) Fast and sensitive protein alignment using
655 DIAMOND. Nature Methods **12**:59–60.

656 Buels R., Yao E., Diesh C.M., Hayes R.D., Munoz-Torres M., Helt G., Goodstein D.M.,
657 Elsik C.G., Lewis S.E., Stein L., Holmes I.H. (2016) JBrowse: a dynamic web platform
658 for genome visualization and analysis. Genome Biology **17**:66.

659 Cantalapiedra C.P., Hernández-Plaza A., Letunic I., Bork P., Huerta-Cepas J. (2021)
660 eggNOG-mapper v2: Functional Annotation, Orthology Assignments, and Domain
661 Prediction at the Metagenomic Scale. Molecular Biology and Evolution **38**:5825–5829.

662 Caspi R., Billington R., Keseler I.M., Kothari A., Krummenacker M., Midford P.E., Ong
663 W.K., Paley S., Subhraveti P., Karp P.D. (2020) The MetaCyc database of metabolic
664 pathways and enzymes - a 2019 update. Nucleic Acids Research **48**:D445–D453.

665 Chen C., Wu Y., Li J., Wang X., Zeng Z., Xu J., Liu Y., Feng J., Chen H., He Y., Xia R.
666 (2023) TBtools-II: A “one for all, all for one” bioinformatics platform for biological big-data
667 mining. Molecular Plant **16**:1733–1742.

668 Choudhary N., Hagedorn M., Pucker B. (2026) Out of the blue: Family-wide loss of
669 anthocyanin biosynthesis in Cucurbitaceae. :2025.10.06.680802.

670 Cingolani P., Platts A., Wang L.L., Coon M., Nguyen T., Wang L., Land S.J., Lu X.,
671 Ruden D.M. (2012) A program for annotating and predicting the effects of single
672 nucleotide polymorphisms, SnpEff. Fly **6**:80–92.

673 Clark K., Karsch-Mizrachi I., Lipman D.J., Ostell J., Sayers E.W. (2016) GenBank.
674 Nucleic Acids Research **44**:D67–D72.

675 Clough S.J., Bent A.F. (1998) Floral dip: a simplified method for Agrobacterium-
676 mediated transformation of Arabidopsis thaliana. The Plant Journal: For Cell and
677 Molecular Biology **16**:735–743.

678 Cock P.J.A., Fields C.J., Goto N., Heuer M.L., Rice P.M. (2010) The Sanger FASTQ file
679 format for sequences with quality scores, and the Solexa/Illumina FASTQ variants.
680 *Nucleic Acids Research* **38**:1767–1771.

681 Conesa A., Götz S., García-Gómez J.M., Terol J., Talón M., Robles M. (2005)
682 Blast2GO: a universal tool for annotation, visualization and analysis in functional
683 genomics research. *Bioinformatics* **21**:3674–3676.

684 Darby C.A., Stolzer M., Ropp P.J., Barker D., Durand D. (2017) Xenolog classification.
685 *Bioinformatics* **33**:640–649.

686 Debladis E., Lee T.-F., Huang Y.-J., Lu J.-H., Mathioni S.M., Carpentier M.-C., Llauro C.,
687 Pierron D., Mieulet D., Guiderdoni E., Chen P.-Y., Meyers B.C., Panaud O., Lasserre E.
688 (2020) Construction and characterization of a knock-down RNA interference line of
689 OsNRPD1 in rice (*Oryza sativa* ssp *japonica* cv Nipponbare). *Philosophical Transactions*
690 *of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* **375**:20190338.

691 Demirer G.S., Landry M.P. (2021) Efficient Transient Gene Knock-down in Tobacco
692 Plants Using Carbon Nanocarriers. *Bio-protocol* **11**:e3897.

693 Dereeper A., Bocs S., Rouard M., Guignon V., Ravel S., Tranchant-Dubreuil C., Poncet
694 V., Garsmeur O., Lashermes P., Droc G. (2015) The coffee genome hub: a resource for
695 coffee genomes. *Nucleic Acids Research* 43 (D1) [online] URL:
696 <https://cgspace.cgiar.org/handle/10568/66031> (accessed 27 November 2023).

697 Diesh C., Stevens G.J., Xie P., De Jesus Martinez T., Hershberg E.A., Leung A., Guo E.,
698 Dider S., Zhang J., Bridge C., Hogue G., Duncan A., Morgan M., Flores T., Bimber B.N.,
699 Haw R., Cain S., Buels R.M., Stein L.D., Holmes I.H. (2023) JBrowse 2: a modular
700 genome browser with views of synteny and structural variation. *Genome Biology* **24**:74.

701 Dobin A., Davis C.A., Schlesinger F., Drenkow J., Zaleski C., Jha S., Batut P., Chaisson
702 M., Gingeras T.R. (2013) STAR: ultrafast universal RNA-seq aligner. *Bioinformatics*
703 **29**:15–21.

704 Dobin A., Gingeras T.R. (2015) Mapping RNA-seq Reads with STAR. *Current Protocols*
705 *in Bioinformatics* **51**:11.14.1-11.14.19.

706 Dommes A.B., Gross T., Herbert D.B., Kivivirta K.I., Becker A. (2019) Virus-induced
707 gene silencing: empowering genetics in non-model organisms. *Journal of Experimental*
708 *Botany* **70**:757–770.

709 Droc G., Martin G., Guignon V., Summo M., Sempéré G., Durant E., Soriano A.,
710 Baurens F.-C., Cenci A., Breton C., Shah T., Aury J.-M., Ge X.-J., Harrison P.H.,
711 Yahiaoui N., D'Hont A., Rouard M. (2022) The banana genome hub: a community
712 database for genomics in the Musaceae. *Horticulture Research* **9**:uhac221.

713 Dubos C., Stracke R., Grotewold E., Weisshaar B., Martin C., Lepiniec L. (2010) MYB
714 transcription factors in Arabidopsis. *Trends in Plant Science* **15**:573–581.

715 Durairaj J., Waterhouse A.M., Mets T., Brodiazhenko T., Abdullah M., Studer G.,
716 Tauriello G., Akdel M., Andreeva A., Bateman A., Tenson T., Hauryliuk V., Schwede T.,

- 717 Pereira J. (2023) Uncovering new families and folds in the natural protein universe.
718 Nature **622**:646–653.
- 719 Eisen J.A. (1998) Phylogenomics: Improving Functional Predictions for Uncharacterized
720 Genes by Evolutionary Analysis. Genome Research **8**:163–167.
- 721 Emms D.M., Kelly S. (2019) OrthoFinder: phylogenetic orthology inference for
722 comparative genomics. Genome Biology **20**:238.
- 723 Emms D.M., Kelly S. (2022) SHOOT: phylogenetic gene search and ortholog inference.
724 Genome Biology **23**:85.
- 725 Fernandez-Pozo N., Menda N., Edwards J.D., Saha S., Teclé I.Y., Strickler S.R.,
726 Bombarely A., Fisher-York T., Pujar A., Foerster H., Yan A., Mueller L.A. (2015) The Sol
727 Genomics Network (SGN)--from genotype to phenotype to breeding. Nucleic Acids
728 Research **43**:D1036-1041.
- 729 Fiddes I.T., Armstrong J., Diekhans M., Nachtweide S., Kronenberg Z.N., Underwood
730 J.G., Gordon D., Earl D., Keane T., Eichler E.E., Haussler D., Stanke M., Paten B.
731 (2018) Comparative Annotation Toolkit (CAT)—simultaneous clade and personal
732 genome annotation. Genome Research **28**:1029–1038.
- 733 Flynn J.M., Hubley R., Goubert C., Rosen J., Clark A.G., Feschotte C., Smit A.F. (2020)
734 RepeatModeler2 for automated genomic discovery of transposable element families.
735 Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences **117**:9451–9457.
- 736 Fo K., Chuah Y.S., Foo H., Davey E.E., Fullwood M., Thibault G., Mutwil M. (2023)
737 PlantConnectome: knowledge networks encompassing >100,000 plant article
738 abstracts. :2023.07.11.548541. [online] URL:
739 <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2023.07.11.548541v2> (accessed 28 January
740 2024).
- 741 Fuentes D., Molina M., Chorostecki U., Capella-Gutiérrez S., Marcet-Houben M.,
742 Gabaldón T. (2022) PhylomeDB V5: an expanding repository for genome-wide
743 catalogues of annotated gene phylogenies. Nucleic Acids Research **50**:D1062–D1068.
- 744 Gabriel L., Becker F., Hoff K.J., Stanke M. (2024) Tiberius: end-to-end deep learning
745 with an HMM for gene prediction. Bioinformatics **40**:btac685.
- 746 Gabriel L., Brūna T., Hoff K.J., Ebel M., Lomsadze A., Borodovsky M., Stanke M. (2023)
747 BRAKER3: Fully Automated Genome Annotation Using RNA-Seq and Protein Evidence
748 with GeneMark-ETP, AUGUSTUS and TSEBRA. :2023.06.10.544449. [online] URL:
749 <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2023.06.10.544449v1> (accessed 20 July 2023).
- 750 Gallaher S.D., Craig R.J., Ganesan I., Purvine S.O., McCorkle S.R., Grimwood J.,
751 Strenkert D., Davidi L., Roth M.S., Jeffers T.L., Lipton M.S., Niyogi K.K., Schmutz J.,
752 Theg S.M., Blaby-Haas C.E., Merchant S.S. (2021) Widespread polycistronic gene
753 expression in green algae. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences
754 **118**:e2017714118.

755 García-Ríos M., Fujita T., LaRosa P.C., Locy R.D., Clithero J.M., Bressan R.A., Csonka
756 L.N. (1997) Cloning of a polycistronic cDNA from tomato encoding gamma-glutamyl
757 kinase and gamma-glutamyl phosphate reductase. *Proceedings of the National*
758 *Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **94**:8249–8254.

759 Gene Ontology Consortium (2021) The Gene Ontology resource: enriching a GOld mine.
760 *Nucleic Acids Research* **49**:D325–D334.

761 Gloss A.D., Vergnol A., Morton T.C., Laurin P.J., Roux F., Bergelson J. (2022) Genome-
762 wide association mapping within a local *Arabidopsis thaliana* population more fully
763 reveals the genetic architecture for defensive metabolite diversity. *Philosophical*
764 *Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* **377**:20200512.

765 Goodstein D.M., Shu S., Howson R., Neupane R., Hayes R.D., Fazo J., Mitros T., Dirks
766 W., Hellsten U., Putnam N., Rokhsar D.S. (2012) Phytozome: a comparative platform for
767 green plant genomics. *Nucleic Acids Research* **40**:D1178–D1186.

768 GrandOmics (2023) NextDenovo. [online] URL:
769 <https://github.com/Nextomics/NextDenovo> (accessed 11 March 2023).

770 Grimplet J., Adam-Blondon A.-F., Bert P.-F., Bitz O., Cantu D., Davies C., Delrot S.,
771 Pezzotti M., Rombauts S., Cramer G.R. (2014) The grapevine gene nomenclature
772 system. *BMC Genomics* **15**:1077.

773 Grünig N., Pucker B. (2025) CoExpPhylo – a novel pipeline for biosynthesis gene
774 discovery. *BMC Genomics* **26**:807.

775 Grützner R., Martin P., Horn C., Mortensen S., Cram E.J., Lee-Parsons C.W.T.,
776 Stuttmann J., Marillonnet S. (2021) High-efficiency genome editing in plants mediated by
777 a Cas9 gene containing multiple introns. *Plant Communications* **2**:100135.

778 Guignon V., Toure A., Droc G., Dufayard J.-F., Conte M., Rouard M. (2021)
779 GreenPhylDB v5: a comparative pangenomic database for plant genomes. *Nucleic Acids*
780 *Research* **49**:D1464–D1471.

781 Guizard S., Miedzinska K., Smith J., Smith J., Kuo R.I., Davey M., Archibald A., Watson
782 M. (2023) nf-core/isoseq: simple gene and isoform annotation with PacBio Iso-Seq long-
783 read sequencing. *Bioinformatics* **39**:btad150.

784 Haak M., Vinke S., Keller W., Droste J., Rückert C., Kalinowski J., Pucker B. (2018) High
785 Quality de Novo Transcriptome Assembly of *Croton tiglium*. *Frontiers in Molecular*
786 *Biosciences* **5** [online] URL:
787 <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmolb.2018.00062/full> (accessed 8 August
788 2020).

789 Hadish J. (2023) Predicting Phenotypic Traits Using a Massive RNA-seq Dataset.
790 [online] URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/10183151> (accessed 8 January 2026).

791 Harris C.D., Torrance E.L., Raymann K., Bobay L.-M. (2021) CoreCruncher: Fast and
792 Robust Construction of Core Genomes in Large Prokaryotic Data Sets. *Molecular*
793 *Biology and Evolution* **38**:727–734.

- 794 Hart A.J., Ginzburg S., Xu M. (Sam), Fisher C.R., Rahmatpour N., Mitton J.B., Paul R.,
795 Wegrzyn J.L. (2020) EnTAP: Bringing faster and smarter functional annotation to non-
796 model eukaryotic transcriptomes. *Molecular Ecology Resources* **20**:591–604.
- 797 Holm L. (2022) Dali server: structural unification of protein families. *Nucleic Acids*
798 *Research* **50**:W210–W215.
- 799 Holst F., Bolger A.M., Kindel F., Günther C., Maß J., Triesch S., Kiel N., Saadat N.,
800 Ebenhöf O., Usadel B., Schwacke R., Weber A.P.M., Bolger M.E., Denton A.K. (2025)
801 Helixer: ab initio prediction of primary eukaryotic gene models combining deep learning
802 and a hidden Markov model. *Nature Methods*:1–8.
- 803 Hu X., Friedberg I. (2019) SwiftOrtho: A fast, memory-efficient, multiple genome
804 orthology classifier. *GigaScience* **8**:giz118.
- 805 Huala E., Dickerman A.W., Garcia-Hernandez M., Weems D., Reiser L., LaFond F.,
806 Hanley D., Kiphart D., Zhuang M., Huang W., Mueller L.A., Bhattacharyya D., Bhaya D.,
807 Sobral B.W., Beavis W., Meinke D.W., Town C.D., Somerville C., Rhee S.Y. (2001) The
808 Arabidopsis Information Resource (TAIR): a comprehensive database and web-based
809 information retrieval, analysis, and visualization system for a model plant. *Nucleic Acids*
810 *Research* **29**:102–105.
- 811 Huerta-Cepas J., Szklarczyk D., Heller D., Hernández-Plaza A., Forslund S.K., Cook H.,
812 Mende D.R., Letunic I., Rattei T., Jensen L.J., von Mering C., Bork P. (2019) eggNOG
813 5.0: a hierarchical, functionally and phylogenetically annotated orthology resource based
814 on 5090 organisms and 2502 viruses. *Nucleic Acids Research* **47**:D309–D314.
- 815 Huynh-Thu V.A., Geurts P. (2018) dynGENIE3: dynamical GENIE3 for the inference of
816 gene networks from time series expression data. *Scientific Reports* **8**:3384.
- 817 Huynh-Thu V.A., Irrthum A., Wehenkel L., Geurts P. (2010) Inferring Regulatory
818 Networks from Expression Data Using Tree-Based Methods. *PLOS ONE* **5**:e12776.
- 819 Irmisch S., Jo S., Roach C.R., Jancsik S., Man Saint Yuen M., Madilao L.L., O’Neil-
820 Johnson M., Williams R., Withers S.G., Bohlmann J. (2018) Discovery of UDP-
821 Glycosyltransferases and BAHD-Acyltransferases Involved in the Biosynthesis of the
822 Antidiabetic Plant Metabolite Montbretin A. *The Plant Cell* **30**:1864–1886.
- 823 Irmisch S., Ruebsam H., Jancsik S., Man Saint Yuen M., Madilao L.L., Bohlmann J.
824 (2019) Flavonol Biosynthesis Genes and Their Use in Engineering the Plant Antidiabetic
825 Metabolite Montbretin A. *Plant Physiology* **180**:1277–1290.
- 826 James G.V., Patel V., Nordström K.J.V., Klasen J.R., Salomé P.A., Weigel D.,
827 Schneeberger K. (2013) User guide for mapping-by-sequencing in Arabidopsis. *Genome*
828 *Biology* **14**:R61.
- 829 Jones P., Binns D., Chang H.-Y., Fraser M., Li W., McAnulla C., McWilliam H., Maslen
830 J., Mitchell A., Nuka G., Pesseat S., Quinn A.F., Sangrador-Vegas A., Scheremetjew M.,
831 Yong S.-Y., Lopez R., Hunter S. (2014) InterProScan 5: genome-scale protein function
832 classification. *Bioinformatics* **30**:1236–1240.

- 833 Julca I., Tan Q.W., Mutwil M. (2023) Toward kingdom-wide analyses of gene expression.
834 *Trends in Plant Science* **28**:235–249.
- 835 Jumper J., Evans R., Pritzel A., Green T., Figurnov M., Ronneberger O.,
836 Tunyasuvunakool K., Bates R., Žídek A., Potapenko A., Bridgland A., Meyer C., Kohl
837 S.A.A., Ballard A.J., Cowie A., Romera-Paredes B., Nikolov S., Jain R., Adler J., Back
838 T., Petersen S., Reiman D., Clancy E., Zielinski M., Steinegger M., Pacholska M.,
839 Berghammer T., Bodenstein S., Silver D., Vinyals O., Senior A.W., Kavukcuoglu K.,
840 Kohli P., Hassabis D. (2021) Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold.
841 *Nature* **596**:583–589.
- 842 Kalyaanamoorthy S., Minh B.Q., Wong T.K.F., von Haeseler A., Jermiin L.S. (2017)
843 ModelFinder: fast model selection for accurate phylogenetic estimates. *Nature Methods*
844 **14**:587–589.
- 845 Kamal S.M., Simpson D.J., Wang Z., Gänzle M., Römling U. (2021) Horizontal
846 Transmission of Stress Resistance Genes Shape the Ecology of Beta- and Gamma-
847 Proteobacteria. *Frontiers in Microbiology* **12** [online] URL:
848 <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/microbiology/articles/10.3389/fmicb.2021.696522/full>
849 (accessed 8 January 2026).
- 850 Kanehisa M., Furumichi M., Sato Y., Kawashima M., Ishiguro-Watanabe M. (2023)
851 KEGG for taxonomy-based analysis of pathways and genomes. *Nucleic Acids Research*
852 **51**:D587–D592.
- 853 Kanehisa M., Goto S. (2000) KEGG: Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes.
854 *Nucleic Acids Research* **28**:27–30.
- 855 Kasif S., Steffen M. (2010) Biochemical networks: The evolution of gene annotation.
856 *Nature Chemical Biology* **6**:4–5.
- 857 Keilwagen J., Hartung F., Grau J. (2019) GeMoMa: Homology-Based Gene Prediction
858 Utilizing Intron Position Conservation and RNA-seq Data. *Methods in Molecular Biology*
859 (Clifton, NJ) **1962**:161–177.
- 860 Keilwagen J., Wenk M., Erickson J.L., Schattat M.H., Grau J., Hartung F. (2016) Using
861 intron position conservation for homology-based gene prediction. *Nucleic Acids*
862 *Research* **44**:e89.
- 863 van Kempen M., Kim S.S., Tumescheit C., Mirdita M., Lee J., Gilchrist C.L.M., Söding J.,
864 Steinegger M. (2024) Fast and accurate protein structure search with Foldseek. *Nature*
865 *Biotechnology* **42**:243–246.
- 866 Kim D., Paggi J.M., Park C., Bennett C., Salzberg S.L. (2019) Graph-based genome
867 alignment and genotyping with HISAT2 and HISAT-genotype. *Nature Biotechnology*
868 **37**:907–915.
- 869 Kirilenko B.M., Munegowda C., Osipova E., Jebb D., Sharma V., Blumer M., Morales
870 A.E., Ahmed A.-W., Kontopoulos D.-G., Hilgers L., Lindblad-Toh K., Karlsson E.K.,
871 Zoonomia Consortium†, Hiller M. (2023) Integrating gene annotation with orthology
872 inference at scale. *Science (New York, NY)* **380**:eabn3107.

873 Kleinboelting N., Huep G., Kloetgen A., Viehoveer P., Weisshaar B. (2012) GABI-Kat
874 SimpleSearch: new features of the Arabidopsis thaliana T-DNA mutant database.
875 Nucleic Acids Research **40**:D1211–D1215.

876 Kolmogorov M., Yuan J., Lin Y., Pevzner P.A. (2019) Assembly of long, error-prone
877 reads using repeat graphs. Nature Biotechnology **37**:540–546.

878 Krishnamurthy N., Brown D.P., Kirshner D., Sjölander K. (2006) PhyloFacts: an online
879 structural phylogenomic encyclopedia for protein functional and structural classification.
880 Genome Biology **7**:R83.

881 Kuznetsov D., Tegenfeldt F., Manni M., Seppey M., Berkeley M., Kriventseva E.V.,
882 Zdobnov E.M. (2023) OrthoDB v11: annotation of orthologs in the widest sampling of
883 organismal diversity. Nucleic Acids Research **51**:D445–D451.

884 Lamesch P., Berardini T.Z., Li D., Swarbreck D., Wilks C., Sasidharan R., Muller R.,
885 Dreher K., Alexander D.L., Garcia-Hernandez M., Karthikeyan A.S., Lee C.H., Nelson
886 W.D., Ploetz L., Singh S., Wensel A., Huala E. (2012) The Arabidopsis Information
887 Resource (TAIR): improved gene annotation and new tools. Nucleic Acids Research
888 **40**:D1202–D1210.

889 Langfelder P., Horvath S. (2008) WGCNA: an R package for weighted correlation
890 network analysis. BMC Bioinformatics **9**:559.

891 Langschied F., Bordin N., Cosentino S., Fuentes-Palacios D., Glover N., Hiller M., Hu Y.,
892 Huerta-Cepas J., Coelho L.P., Iwasaki W., Majidian S., Manzano-Morales S., Persson
893 E., Richards T.A., Gabaldón T., Sonnhammer E., Thomas P.D., Dessimoz C.,
894 Ebersberger I. (2024) Quest for Orthologs in the Era of Biodiversity Genomics. Genome
895 Biology and Evolution **16**:evae224.

896 Lau W., Sattely E.S. (2015) Six enzymes from mayapple that complete the biosynthetic
897 pathway to the etoposide aglycone. Science (New York, NY) **349**:1224–1228.

898 Lee T., Lee I. (2021) Genome-Wide Association Studies in Arabidopsis thaliana:
899 Statistical Analysis and Network-Based Augmentation of Signals. Methods in Molecular
900 Biology (Clifton, NJ) **2200**:187–210.

901 Lee H.Y., Seo J.-S., Cho J.H., Jung H., Kim J.-K., Lee J.S., Rhee S., Choi Y.D. (2013)
902 Oryza sativa COI Homologues Restore Jasmonate Signal Transduction in Arabidopsis
903 coi1-1 Mutants. PLOS ONE **8**:e52802.

904 Letunic I., Bork P. (2021) Interactive Tree Of Life (iTOL) v5: an online tool for
905 phylogenetic tree display and annotation. Nucleic Acids Research **49**:W293–W296.

906 Li F., Chen J., Luo W., Liu J., Chen G., Shuai B., Hou Z., Gan Z., Zhao H., Zhan P., Bi
907 C., Wang Z., Hu H., Wang S. (2025) DeepPGDB: A novel paradigm for AI-guided
908 interactive plant genomic database. Plant Communications **6**:101494.

909 Li L., Dannenfelser R., Zhu Y., Hejduk N., Segarra S., Yao V. (2023) Joint embedding of
910 biological networks for cross-species functional alignment. Bioinformatics **39**:btad529.

- 911 Lipman D.J., Pearson W.R. (1985) Rapid and Sensitive Protein Similarity Searches.
912 Science **227**:1435–1441.
- 913 Lohse M., Nagel A., Herter T., May P., Schroda M., Zrenner R., Tohge T., Fernie A.R.,
914 Stitt M., Usadel B. (2014) Mercator: a fast and simple web server for genome scale
915 functional annotation of plant sequence data. Plant, Cell & Environment **37**:1250–1258.
- 916 Lu R., Martin-Hernandez A.M., Peart J.R., Malcuit I., Baulcombe D.C. (2003) Virus-
917 induced gene silencing in plants. Methods (San Diego, Calif) **30**:296–303.
- 918 Ludwig J., Mrázek J. (2024) OrthoRefine: automated enhancement of prior ortholog
919 identification via synteny. BMC Bioinformatics **25**:163.
- 920 Lyons E., Pedersen B., Kane J., Alam M., Ming R., Tang H., Wang X., Bowers J.,
921 Paterson A., Lisch D., Freeling M. (2008) Finding and Comparing Syntenic Regions
922 among Arabidopsis and the Outgroups Papaya, Poplar, and Grape: CoGe with Rosids.
923 Plant Physiology **148**:1772–1781.
- 924 Mahood E.H., Kruse L.H., Moghe G.D. (2020) Machine learning: A powerful tool for gene
925 function prediction in plants. Applications in Plant Sciences **8**:e11376.
- 926 Majidian S., Hadziahmetovic A., Langschieb F., Pascarelli S., Prieto-Baños S., Rojas-
927 Vargas J., Arvestad L., Cheema J., Cosentino S., Ebersberger I., Kuzmin E., Nevers Y.,
928 Romashchenko N., Stolzer M., Wang Y., Vesztröcy A.W., Xiao Y., Braun E.L., Dessimoz
929 C., Diallo A.B., Durand D., Fang G., Gabaldón T., Glover N., Liberles D.A., McWhite C.,
930 Sonnhammer E.L.L., Thomas P.D., Ouangraoua A., Julca I., Quest for Orthologs
931 Consortium (2025) Quest for Orthologs in the era of Data Deluge and AI: Challenges
932 and Innovations in Orthology Prediction and Data Integration. Journal of Molecular
933 Evolution **93**:702–719.
- 934 Majidian S., Nevers Y., Yazdizadeh Kharrazi A., Warwick Vesztröcy A., Pascarelli S.,
935 Moi D., Glover N., Altenhoff A.M., Dessimoz C. (2025) Orthology inference at scale with
936 FastOMA. Nature Methods **22**:269–272.
- 937 Manni M., Berkeley M.R., Seppey M., Simão F.A., Zdobnov E.M. (2021) BUSCO
938 Update: Novel and Streamlined Workflows along with Broader and Deeper Phylogenetic
939 Coverage for Scoring of Eukaryotic, Prokaryotic, and Viral Genomes. Molecular Biology
940 and Evolution **38**:4647–4654.
- 941 Mariault L., Puginier C., Keller J., El Baidouri M., Delaux P.-M. (2025) Mechanisms,
942 detection, and impact of horizontal gene transfer in plant functional evolution. The Plant
943 Cell **37**:koaf195.
- 944 Marks R.A., Hotaling S., Frandsen P.B., VanBuren R. (2021) Representation and
945 participation across 20 years of plant genome sequencing. Nature Plants **7**:1571–1578.
- 946 Mascher M., Jost M., Kuon J.-E., Himmelbach A., Aßfalg A., Beier S., Scholz U., Graner
947 A., Stein N. (2014) Mapping-by-sequencing accelerates forward genetics in barley.
948 Genome Biology **15**:R78.

- 949 Miller J.B., Pickett B.D., Ridge P.G. (2019) JustOrthologs: a fast, accurate and user-
950 friendly ortholog identification algorithm. *Bioinformatics* **35**:546–552.
- 951 Mistry J., Chuguransky S., Williams L., Qureshi M., Salazar G.A., Sonnhammer E.L.L.,
952 Tosatto S.C.E., Paladin L., Raj S., Richardson L.J., Finn R.D., Bateman A. (2021) Pfam:
953 The protein families database in 2021. *Nucleic Acids Research* **49**:D412–D419.
- 954 Moriya Y., Itoh M., Okuda S., Yoshizawa A.C., Kanehisa M. (2007) KAAS: an automatic
955 genome annotation and pathway reconstruction server. *Nucleic Acids Research*
956 **35**:W182–W185.
- 957 Muñoz C., Di Genova A., Maass A., Orellana A., Hinrichsen P., Aravena A. (2014) VITIS
958 VINIFERA GENOME ANNOTATION IMPROVEMENT USING NEXT-GENERATION
959 SEQUENCING TECHNOLOGIES AND NCBI PUBLIC DATA. *Acta Horticulturae*:349–
960 356.
- 961 Naake T., Zhu F., Alseekh S., Scossa F., Perez de Souza L., Borghi M., Brotman Y.,
962 Mori T., Nakabayashi R., Tohge T., Fernie A.R. (2023) Genome-wide association
963 studies identify loci controlling specialized seed metabolites in *Arabidopsis*. *Plant*
964 *Physiology*:kiad511.
- 965 Naish M., Alonge M., Wlodzimierz P., Tock A.J., Abramson B.W., Schmücker A.,
966 Mandáková T., Jamge B., Lambing C., Kuo P., Yelina N., Hartwick N., Colt K., Smith
967 L.M., Ton J., Kakutani T., Martienssen R.A., Schneeberger K., Lysak M.A., Berger F.,
968 Bousios A., Michael T.P., Schatz M.C., Henderson I.R. (2021) The genetic and
969 epigenetic landscape of the *Arabidopsis* centromeres. *Science* **374**:eabi7489.
- 970 Naithani S., Gupta P., Preece J., D'Eustachio P., Elser J.L., Garg P., Dikeman D.A., Kiff
971 J., Cook J., Olson A., Wei S., Tello-Ruiz M.K., Mundo A.F., Munoz-Pomer A.,
972 Mohammed S., Cheng T., Bolton E., Papatheodorou I., Stein L., Ware D., Jaiswal P.
973 (2020) Plant Reactome: a knowledgebase and resource for comparative pathway
974 analysis. *Nucleic Acids Research* **48**:D1093–D1103.
- 975 Napoli C., Lemieux C., Jorgensen R. (1990) Introduction of a Chimeric Chalcone
976 Synthase Gene into *Petunia* Results in Reversible Co-Suppression of Homologous
977 Genes in trans. *The Plant Cell* **2**:279–289.
- 978 Natarajan S., Pucker B. (2025) DupyliCate - mining, classifying, and characterizing gene
979 duplications. [online] URL: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.10.10.681656>
- 980 Nehrt N.L., Clark W.T., Radivojac P., Hahn M.W. (2011) Testing the ortholog conjecture
981 with comparative functional genomic data from mammals. *PLoS computational biology*
982 **7**:e1002073.
- 983 Nurk S., Walenz B.P., Rhie A., Vollger M.R., Logsdon G.A., Grothe R., Miga K.H.,
984 Eichler E.E., Phillippy A.M., Koren S. (2020) HiCanu: accurate assembly of segmental
985 duplications, satellites, and allelic variants from high-fidelity long reads. *Genome*
986 *Research*:gr.263566.120.

- 987 de Oliveira J.A.V.S., Choudhary N., Meckoni S.N., Nowak M.S., Hagedorn M., Pucker B.
988 (2026) Cookbook for plant genome sequences. BMC Genomics [online] URL:
989 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-026-12623-z> (accessed 7 February 2026).
- 990 O'Malley R.C., Barragan C.C., Ecker J.R. (2015) A User's Guide to the Arabidopsis T-
991 DNA Insertional Mutant Collections. Methods in molecular biology (Clifton, NJ)
992 **1284**:323–342.
- 993 Ou S., Collins T., Qiu Y., Seetharam A.S., Menard C.C., Manchanda N., Gent J.I.,
994 Schatz M.C., Anderson S.N., Hufford M.B., Hirsch C.N. (2022) Differences in activity and
995 stability drive transposable element variation in tropical and temperate maize.
996 :2022.10.09.511471. [online] URL:
997 <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2022.10.09.511471v1> (accessed 28 January
998 2024).
- 999 Ou S., Su W., Liao Y., Chougule K., Agda J.R.A., Hellinga A.J., Lugo C.S.B., Elliott T.A.,
1000 Ware D., Peterson T., Jiang N., Hirsch C.N., Hufford M.B. (2019) Benchmarking
1001 transposable element annotation methods for creation of a streamlined, comprehensive
1002 pipeline. Genome Biology **20**:275.
- 1003 Ovek Baydar D., Rauluseviciute I., Aronsen D.R., Blanc-Mathieu R., Bonthuis I.,
1004 de Beukelaer H., Ferenc K., Jegou A., Kumar V., Lemma R.B., Lucas J., Pochon M.,
1005 Yun C.M., Ramalingam V., Deshpande S.S., Patel A., Marinov G.K., Wang A.T., Aguirre
1006 A., Castro-Mondragon J.A., Baranasic D., Chèneby J., Gundersen S., Johansen M.,
1007 Khan A., Kuijjer M.L., Hovig E., Lenhard B., Sandelin A., Vandepoele K., Wasserman
1008 W.W., Parcy F., Kundaje A., Mathelier A. (2025) JASPAR 2026: expansion of
1009 transcription factor binding profiles and integration of deep learning models. Nucleic
1010 Acids Research:gkaf1209.
- 1011 Palmer J. (2019) funannotate v1.5.3. [online] URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/2604804>
1012 (accessed 27 November 2023).
- 1013 Price M.N., Dehal P.S., Arkin A.P. (2010) FastTree 2 – Approximately Maximum-
1014 Likelihood Trees for Large Alignments. PLOS ONE **5**:e9490.
- 1015 Pucker B. (2022) Automatic identification and annotation of MYB gene family members
1016 in plants. BMC Genomics **23**:220.
- 1017 Pucker B., Holtgräwe D., Sörensen T.R., Stracke R., Viehöver P., Weisshaar B. (2016) A
1018 De Novo Genome Sequence Assembly of the Arabidopsis thaliana Accession
1019 Niederenz-1 Displays Presence/Absence Variation and Strong Synteny. PLOS ONE
1020 **11**:e0164321.
- 1021 Pucker B., Irisarri I., Vries J. de, Xu B. (2022) Plant genome sequence assembly in the
1022 era of long reads: Progress, challenges and future directions. Quantitative Plant Biology
1023 **3**:e5.
- 1024 Pucker B., Kleinbölting N., Weisshaar B. (2021) Large scale genomic rearrangements in
1025 selected Arabidopsis thaliana T-DNA lines are caused by T-DNA insertion mutagenesis.
1026 BMC Genomics **22**:599.

- 1027 Pucker B., Pandey A., Weisshaar B., Stracke R. (2020) The R2R3-MYB gene family in
1028 banana (*Musa acuminata*): Genome-wide identification, classification and expression
1029 patterns. *PLOS ONE* **15**:e0239275.
- 1030 Pucker B., Reiher F., Schilbert H.M. (2020) Automatic Identification of Players in the
1031 Flavonoid Biosynthesis with Application on the Biomedical Plant *Croton tiglium*. *Plants*
1032 **9**:1103.
- 1033 Ramos-González M., Ramos-González V., Arvanitidou C., Hernández-García J., García-
1034 González M., Romero-Campero F.J. (2023) PharaohFUN: PHylogenomic Analysis for
1035 pLAnt prOtein History and FUNction elucidation. :2023.08.01.551440. [online] URL:
1036 <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2023.08.01.551440v1> (accessed 28 January
1037 2024).
- 1038 Rempel A., Choudhary N., Pucker B. (2023) KIPes3: Automatic annotation of
1039 biosynthesis pathways. *PLOS ONE* **18**:e0294342.
- 1040 Rennie M.L., Oliver M.R. (2025) Emerging frontiers in protein structure prediction
1041 following the AlphaFold revolution. *Journal of The Royal Society Interface* **22**:20240886.
- 1042 Rhie A., Walenz B.P., Koren S., Phillippy A.M. (2020) Merqury: reference-free quality,
1043 completeness, and phasing assessment for genome assemblies. *Genome Biology*
1044 **21**:245.
- 1045 Riehl K., Riccio C., Miska E.A., Hemberg M. (2022) TransposonUltimate: software for
1046 transposon classification, annotation and detection. *Nucleic Acids Research* **50**:e64.
- 1047 Rosso M.G., Li Y., Strizhov N., Reiss B., Dekker K., Weisshaar B. (2003) An *Arabidopsis*
1048 *thaliana* T-DNA mutagenized population (GABI-Kat) for flanking sequence tag-based
1049 reverse genetics. *Plant Molecular Biology* **53**:247–259.
- 1050 Ruiz M.T., Voinnet O., Baulcombe D.C. (1998) Initiation and Maintenance of Virus-
1051 Induced Gene Silencing. *The Plant Cell* **10**:937–946.
- 1052 Samuilov S., Rademacher N., Brilhaus D., Flachbart S., Arab L., Kopriva S., Weber
1053 A.P.M., Mettler-Altmann T., Rennenberg H. (2018) Knock-Down of the Phosphoserine
1054 Phosphatase Gene Effects Rather N- Than S-Metabolism in *Arabidopsis thaliana*.
1055 *Frontiers in Plant Science* **9** [online] URL:
1056 <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpls.2018.01830> (accessed 6 January 2024).
- 1057 Sasaki E., Köcher T., Filiault D.L., Nordborg M. (2021) Revisiting a GWAS peak in
1058 *Arabidopsis thaliana* reveals possible confounding by genetic heterogeneity. *Heredity*
1059 **127**:245–252.
- 1060 Sayers E.W., Cavanaugh M., Clark K., Ostell J., Pruitt K.D., Karsch-Mizrachi I. (2020)
1061 GenBank. *Nucleic Acids Research* **48**:D84–D86.
- 1062 Schilbert H.M., Pucker B., Ries D., Viehöver P., Micic Z., Dreyer F., Beckmann K.,
1063 Wittkop B., Weisshaar B., Holtgräwe D. (2022) Mapping-by-Sequencing Reveals
1064 Genomic Regions Associated with Seed Quality Parameters in *Brassica napus*. *Genes*
1065 **13**:1131.

- 1066 Schilbert H.M., Schöne M., Baier T., Busche M., Viehöver P., Weisshaar B., Holtgräwe
1067 D. (2021) Characterization of the Brassica napus Flavonol Synthase Gene Family
1068 Reveals Bifunctional Flavonol Synthases. *Frontiers in Plant Science* **12** [online] URL:
1069 <https://www.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fpls.2021.733762> (accessed 16 February
1070 2022).
- 1071 Schneeberger K., Weigel D. (2011) Fast-forward genetics enabled by new sequencing
1072 technologies. *Trends in Plant Science* **16**:282–288.
- 1073 Shafin K., Pesout T., Lorig-Roach R., Haukness M., Olsen H.E., Bosworth C., Armstrong
1074 J., Tigyi K., Maurer N., Koren S., Sedlazeck F.J., Marschall T., Mayes S., Costa V., Zook
1075 J.M., Liu K.J., Kilburn D., Sorensen M., Munson K.M., Vollger M.R., Monlong J.,
1076 Garrison E., Eichler E.E., Salama S., Haussler D., Green R.E., Akeson M., Phillippy A.,
1077 Miga K.H., Carnevali P., Jain M., Paten B. (2020) Nanopore sequencing and the Shasta
1078 toolkit enable efficient de novo assembly of eleven human genomes. *Nature*
1079 *Biotechnology* **38**:1044–1053.
- 1080 Shannon P., Markiel A., Ozier O., Baliga N.S., Wang J.T., Ramage D., Amin N.,
1081 Schwikowski B., Ideker T. (2003) Cytoscape: a software environment for integrated
1082 models of biomolecular interaction networks. *Genome Research* **13**:2498–2504.
- 1083 Shi X., Cao S., Wang X., Huang S., Wang Y., Liu Z., Liu W., Leng X., Peng Y., Wang N.,
1084 Wang Y., Ma Z., Xu X., Zhang F., Xue H., Zhong H., Wang Y., Zhang K., Velt A., Avia
1085 K., Holtgräwe D., Grimplet J., Matus J.T., Ware D., Wu X., Wang H., Liu C., Fang Y.,
1086 Rustenholz C., Cheng Z., Xiao H., Zhou Y. (2023) The complete reference genome for
1087 grapevine (*Vitis vinifera* L.) genetics and breeding. *Horticulture Research* **10**:uhad061.
- 1088 Sielemann K., Hafner A., Pucker B. (2020) The reuse of public datasets in the life
1089 sciences: potential risks and rewards. *PeerJ* **8**:e9954.
- 1090 Sielemann K., Pucker B., Orsini E., Elashry A., Schulte L., Viehöver P., Müller A.E.,
1091 Schechert A., Weisshaar B., Holtgräwe D. (2023) Genomic characterization of a
1092 nematode tolerance locus in sugar beet. *BMC Genomics* **24**:748.
- 1093 Simão F.A., Waterhouse R.M., Ioannidis P., Kriventseva E.V., Zdobnov E.M. (2015)
1094 BUSCO: assessing genome assembly and annotation completeness with single-copy
1095 orthologs. *Bioinformatics* **31**:3210–3212.
- 1096 Singh K.S., van der Hooft J.J.J., van Wees S.C.M., Medema M.H. (2022) Integrative
1097 omics approaches for biosynthetic pathway discovery in plants. *Natural Product Reports*
1098 **39**:1876–1896.
- 1099 Sjölander K. (2004) Phylogenomic inference of protein molecular function: advances and
1100 challenges. *Bioinformatics (Oxford, England)* **20**:170–179.
- 1101 Smit A., Hubley R., Green P. (2015) RepeatMasker. [online] URL:
1102 <http://www.repeatmasker.org/>
- 1103 Sreedasyam A., Plott C., Hossain M.S., Lovell J.T., Grimwood J., Jenkins J.W., Daum
1104 C., Barry K., Carlson J., Shu S., Phillips J., Amirebrahimi M., Zane M., Wang M.,
1105 Goodstein D., Haas F.B., Hiss M., Perroud P.-F., Jawdy S.S., Yang Y., Hu R., Johnson

- 1106 J., Kropat J., Gallaher S.D., Lipzen A., Shakirov E.V., Weng X., Torres-Jerez I., Weers
1107 B., Conde D., Pappas M.R., Liu L., Muchlinski A., Jiang H., Shyu C., Huang P.,
1108 Sebastian J., Laiben C., Medlin A., Carey S., Carrell A.A., Chen J.-G., Perales M.,
1109 Swaminathan K., Allona I., Grattapaglia D., Cooper E.A., Tholl D., Vogel J.P., Weston
1110 D.J., Yang X., Brutnell T.P., Kellogg E.A., Baxter I., Udvardi M., Tang Y., Mockler T.C.,
1111 Juenger T.E., Mullet J., Rensing S.A., Tuskan G.A., Merchant S.S., Stacey G., Schmutz
1112 J. (2023) JGI Plant Gene Atlas: an updateable transcriptome resource to improve
1113 functional gene descriptions across the plant kingdom. *Nucleic Acids Research*
1114 **51**:8383–8401.
- 1115 Stambouliau M., Guerrero R.F., Hahn M.W., Radivojac P. (2020) The ortholog
1116 conjecture revisited: the value of orthologs and paralogs in function prediction.
1117 *Bioinformatics* **36**:i219–i226.
- 1118 Stein L.D. (2013) Using GBrowse 2.0 to visualize and share next-generation sequence
1119 data. *Briefings in Bioinformatics* **14**:162–171.
- 1120 Stracke R., Werber M., Weisshaar B. (2001) The R2R3-MYB gene family in *Arabidopsis*
1121 *thaliana*. *Current Opinion in Plant Biology* **4**:447–456.
- 1122 Tang H., Bowers J.E., Wang X., Ming R., Alam M., Paterson A.H. (2008) Synteny and
1123 Collinearity in Plant Genomes. *Science* **320**:486–488.
- 1124 Tang H., Krishnakumar V., Zeng X., Xu Z., Taranto A., Lomas J.S., Zhang Y., Huang Y.,
1125 Wang Y., Yim W.C., Zhang J., Zhang X. (2024) JCVI: A versatile toolkit for comparative
1126 genomics analysis. *iMeta* **3**:e211.
- 1127 Thoben C., Pucker B. (2023) Automatic annotation of the bHLH gene family in plants.
1128 *BMC Genomics* **24**:780.
- 1129 Thomas P.D., Ebert D., Muruganujan A., Mushayahama T., Albou L.-P., Mi H. (2022)
1130 PANTHER: Making genome-scale phylogenetics accessible to all. *Protein Science* **31**:8–
1131 22.
- 1132 de la Torre-López J., Ramírez A., Romero J.R. (2023) Artificial intelligence to automate
1133 the systematic review of scientific literature. *Computing* **105**:2171–2194.
- 1134 Tran N.-V., Greshake Tzovaras B., Ebersberger I. (2018) PhyloProfile: dynamic
1135 visualization and exploration of multi-layered phylogenetic profiles. *Bioinformatics*
1136 **34**:3041–3043.
- 1137 Treangen T.J., Rocha E.P.C. (2011) Horizontal Transfer, Not Duplication, Drives the
1138 Expansion of Protein Families in Prokaryotes. *PLOS Genetics* **7**:e1001284.
- 1139 Varadi M., Anyango S., Deshpande M., Nair S., Natassia C., Yordanova G., Yuan D.,
1140 Stroe O., Wood G., Laydon A., Židek A., Green T., Tunyasuvunakool K., Petersen S.,
1141 Jumper J., Clancy E., Green R., Vora A., Lutfi M., Figurnov M., Cowie A., Hobbs N.,
1142 Kohli P., Kleywegt G., Birney E., Hassabis D., Velankar S. (2022) AlphaFold Protein
1143 Structure Database: massively expanding the structural coverage of protein-sequence
1144 space with high-accuracy models. *Nucleic Acids Research* **50**:D439–D444.

- 1145 Velasco R., Zharkikh A., Troggio M., Cartwright D.A., Cestaro A., Pruss D., Pindo M.,
1146 FitzGerald L.M., Vezzulli S., Reid J., Malacarne G., Iliev D., Coppola G., Wardell B.,
1147 Micheletti D., Macalma T., Facci M., Mitchell J.T., Perazzolli M., Eldredge G., Gatto P.,
1148 Oyzerski R., Moretto M., Gutin N., Stefanini M., Chen Y., Segala C., Davenport C.,
1149 Demattè L., Mraz A., Battilana J., Stormo K., Costa F., Tao Q., Si-Ammour A., Harkins
1150 T., Lackey A., Perbost C., Taillon B., Stella A., Solovyev V., Fawcett J.A., Sterck L.,
1151 Vandepoele K., Grando S.M., Toppo S., Moser C., Lanchbury J., Bogden R., Skolnick
1152 M., Sgaramella V., Bhatnagar S.K., Fontana P., Gutin A., Van de Peer Y., Salamini F.,
1153 Viola R. (2007) A High Quality Draft Consensus Sequence of the Genome of a
1154 Heterozygous Grapevine Variety. *PLoS ONE* **2**:e1326.
- 1155 Velt A., Frommer B., Blanc S., Holtgräwe D., Duchêne É., Dumas V., Grimplet J.,
1156 Hugueney P., Kim C., Lahaye M., Matus J.T., Navarro-Payá D., Orduña L., Tello-Ruiz
1157 M.K., Vitulo N., Ware D., Rustenholz C. (2023) An improved reference of the grapevine
1158 genome reasserts the origin of the PN40024 highly homozygous genotype. *G3*
1159 *Genes|Genomes|Genetics* **13**:jkad067.
- 1160 Vuruputoor V.S., Monyak D., Fetter K.C., Webster C., Bhattarai A., Shrestha B., Zaman
1161 S., Bennett J., McEvoy S.L., Caballero M., Wegrzyn J.L. (2023) Welcome to the big
1162 leaves: Best practices for improving genome annotation in non-model plant genomes.
1163 *Applications in Plant Sciences* **11**:e11533.
- 1164 Wang K., Wang D., Zheng X., Qin A., Zhou J., Guo B., Chen Y., Wen X., Ye W., Zhou
1165 Y., Zhu Y. (2019) Multi-strategic RNA-seq analysis reveals a high-resolution
1166 transcriptional landscape in cotton. *Nature Communications* **10**:4714.
- 1167 Wlodzimierz P., Rabanal F.A., Burns R., Naish M., Primetis E., Scott A., Mandáková T.,
1168 Gorringer N., Tock A.J., Holland D., Fritschi K., Habring A., Lanz C., Patel C., Schlegel
1169 T., Collenberg M., Mielke M., Nordborg M., Roux F., Shirsekar G., Alonso-Blanco C.,
1170 Lysak M.A., Novikova P.Y., Bousios A., Weigel D., Henderson I.R. (2023) Cycles of
1171 satellite and transposon evolution in Arabidopsis centromeres. *Nature* **618**:557–565.
- 1172 Wong T.K.F., Ly-Trong N., Ren H., Baños H., Roger A.J., Susko E., Bielow C., Maio
1173 N.D., Goldman N., Hahn M.W., Huttley G., Lanfear R., Minh B.Q. (2025) IQ-TREE 3:
1174 Phylogenomic Inference Software using Complex Evolutionary Models. [online] URL:
1175 <https://ecoevorxiv.org/repository/view/8916/> (accessed 5 January 2026).
- 1176 Xu L., Dong Z., Fang L., Luo Y., Wei Z., Guo H., Zhang G., Gu Y.Q., Coleman-Derr D.,
1177 Xia Q., Wang Y. (2019) OrthoVenn2: a web server for whole-genome comparison and
1178 annotation of orthologous clusters across multiple species. *Nucleic Acids Research*
1179 **47**:W52–W58.
- 1180 Yu M., Wu J., Zhao C., Qiu J.-L. (2025) Exploring plant protein functions through
1181 structure-based clustering. *Trends in Plant Science* **30**:1111–1118.
- 1182 Zhang R.-G., Shang H.-Y., Milne R.I., Almeida-Silva F., Chen H., Zhou M.-J., Shu H., Jia
1183 K.-H., Van de Peer Y., Ma Y.-P. (2025) SOI: robust identification of orthologous synteny
1184 with the Orthology Index and broad applications in evolutionary genomics. *Nucleic Acids*
1185 *Research* **53**:gkaf320.

1186 Zimmermann I.M., Heim M.A., Weisshaar B., Uhrig J.F. (2004) Comprehensive
1187 identification of *Arabidopsis thaliana* MYB transcription factors interacting with R/B-like
1188 BHLH proteins. *The Plant Journal: For Cell and Molecular Biology* **40**:22–34.

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1191